

Research Article

Suppression of Oxidative Stress and Inflammatory responses are Involved in the Cardioprotective Effect of *Jatropha Tanjorensis* in Wistar Rats Exposed to Doxorubicin

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Abstract: Doxorubicin (DOX) has been reported to cause cardiotoxicity via induction of oxidative stress and inflammatory reactions. Whether *Jatropha tanjorensis*, a popular vegetable rich in flavonoids and polyphenols can ameliorate the toxic effect of doxorubicin exposure remain incompletely studied. Hence this study investigated the ameliorative potential of diethylether extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* on doxorubicin-induced cardiac toxicity in rats. The animals were randomly divided into sixteen groups of five rats per group. Doxorubicin was administered intraperitoneally at 20 mg/kg while the treated groups received the plant extract at 167, 250 and 500 mg/kg for 14, 28 and 42 days. The positive control group was treated with the standard drug, carvedilol. Cardiac damage was confirmed in DOX-treated animals with a significant increase in the levels of cardiac troponin T and I, IL-6, CRP, CK, LDL-C, VLDL-C, Total-CHOL and TG. The activities of ALT, ALP, AST and LDH enzymes were significantly elevated in the untreated DOX-exposed animals for 14, 28 and 42 days while the activities of the antioxidant enzymes, GPx, CAT and SOD were significantly reduced. Treatment with *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf extract significantly ameliorated this derangement in the histo-architecture due to oxidative stress and inflammation as well as regeneration of myocytes and restoration of normal heart architecture. This study suggests that *Jatropha tanjorensis* possesses cardioprotective potential by suppressing oxidative stress and inflammatory responses against doxorubicin-induced cardiac toxicity.

Keywords: cardiac damage, doxorubicin, inflammation, oxidative stress, enzyme markers, *jatropha tanjorensis*

1. Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) continue to be the leading cause of death in both developed and developing countries, accounting for roughly 20% of global deaths each year (Townsend *et al.*, 2022). According to statistics from the American Heart Association and the World Heart Organization, cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are the leading cause of death worldwide (ElSerag and Thurston, 2020). Chronic cardiotoxicity manifests as progressive myocardial dysfunction weeks or even months after doxorubicin (DOX) administration with both early and late onset manifestations. The progression of left ventricular systolic dysfunction to dilated cardiomyopathy and

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Congestive heart failure (CHF) is reported to occur following chemotherapy (Li *et al.*, 2022). Doxorubicin (DOX)-based chemotherapy is the gold standard in cancer treatment; however, its clinical application and therapeutic value are clearly limited by life-threatening cardiotoxicity, which eventually leads to left ventricular dysfunction and congestive heart failure (Lang *et al.*, 2021). Uncontrolled reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation via oxidative damage to biomacromolecules and activation of downstream proapoptotic pathways has been identified as the primary cause of DOX-induced cellular injury and cardiac dysfunction (Jones and Dass, 2022). Furthermore, because of its less active antioxidant network and negligible regenerative capacity, the heart is particularly vulnerable to free radical damage (Meng and Xu, 2022). Interestingly, previous research found that inhibiting oxidative stress and apoptosis was sufficient to alleviate DOX-related cardiac damage and dysfunction (Doroszkó *et al.*, 2020; Jones and Dass, 2022). Many molecules have been developed as cardioprotective adjuvants to combat DOX-induced cardiotoxicity such as beta blockers, angiotensin receptor blockers, amifostine, leucovorin, and erythropoietin (Cadeddu-Dessalvi *et al.*, 2021 Alawode *et al.*, 2021). The main disadvantage of most of these molecules is their undesirable side effects and complications (Kim *et al.*, 2020). Indeed, plants and herbs have been used in the treatment of various diseases and ailments since the dawn of human civilization (Chaachouay *et al.*, 2022). Because medicinal plants contain a variety of valuable phytoconstituents, they are unique in their ability to treat a variety of human ailments (Asiwe *et al.*, 2023). In Nigeria, *Jatropha tanjorensis*, also known as "Hospital too far" or "Catholic vegetable," is a shrub in the Euphorbiaceae family. *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaves, aerial parts, roots and bark have reportedly been used as medicine in various parts of the country. Its leaves have been shown to have hepatoprotective (Alawode *et al.*, 2021; Obum-Nnadi *et al.*, 2022), anticancer (Obum-Nnadi *et al.*, 2022), anti-anemic (Iwu *et al.*, 2021), antiulcer (Babayemi *et al.*, 2021), antioxidant (Alawode *et al.*, 2021), hypolipidemic (Usin *et al.*, 2022) properties. Despite these pharmacological benefits, there is paucity of information in literature on the possible role of *Jatropha tanjorensis* on doxorubicin-induced cardiotoxicity. Hence, this study looks into the cardioprotective effect of *Jatropha tanjorensis* diethylether extract on doxorubicin-induced cardiac damage and possible mechanism of action in Wistar rats.

2. Materials and Methods

Plant

A taxonomist at the Herbarium unit, Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria identified fresh leaves of *Jatropha tanjorensis* collected from Ogbogoro in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. The leaf sample was cataloged with voucher number UPH/P/343 in the herbarium.

Plant Preparation and Extraction

Jatropha tanjorensis leaves were washed, air-dried and ground into a fine powder using an electric blender. The powder (1500 g) was extracted in three cycles with 96% diethylether using a soxhlet extractor. Filter paper was used to filter the crude extract (Whatman No. 4). A rotary vacuum evaporator at 35°C was used to dry the filtrate,

yielding a viscous brownish-colored extract. It was kept in the refrigerator at 4°C till when needed for use.

Phytochemical Screening

The qualitative phytochemical screening was carried out using the method described by Eruotor and colleagues, (2022).

Chemicals and Reagents

The drugs, doxorubicin (DOX) and carvedilol were purchased from Jojan pharmaceutical, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. All other chemicals and reagents used in the study were of analytical grade.

Animals

The animal house, Department of Biology, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt, provided 80 healthy Wistar albino rats of both sexes weighing between 180-220g. They were housed in clean animal cages with adequate ventilation for seven days before being acclimated to the laboratory environment. They were fed standard animal feed and given unlimited access to water. The study was approved by the ethical committee of the University of Port-Harcourt (UPH-REC/2021/028) which followed strictly with National guidelines for animal care and use of animals as well as the Organization of Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD).

Experimental Design

The Wistar albino rats were randomly assigned to 16 groups of 5 rats each in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD). In rats, cardiac damage was induced with a single intraperitoneal injection of 20 mg/kg body weight (Li *et al.*, 2006; Neilan *et al.*, 2006). The dosage of *Jatropha tanjorensis* extract as well as toxicity profile was done in our previous study. However, the study groups were divided as follows:

Group 1 (Normal control) received distilled water for 42 days.

Groups 2 (negative control, 14 days) received 20 mg/kg of DOX for 14 days.

Group 3 (Negative control, 28 days) received 20 mg/kg of DOX for 28 days.

Group 4 (Negative control, 42 days) received 20mg/kg of DOX for 42 days.

Group 5 (Positive control, 14 days) received 20mg/kg of DOX + carvedilol for 14 days.

Group 6 (Positive control, 28 days) received 20mg/kg of DOX + carvedilol for 28 days.

Group 7 (positive control, 42 days) received 20mg/kg of DOX + carvedilol for 42 days.

Group 8: DOX-induced + 167mg/kg of *Jatropha tanjorensis* extract for 14 days

Group 9: DOX-induced + 167mg/kg of *Jatropha tanjorensis* extract for 28 days

Group 10: DOX-induced + 167mg/kg of *Jatropha tanjorensis* extract for 42 days

Group 11: DOX-induced + 250mg/kg of *Jatropha tanjorensis* extract for 14 days

Group 12: DOX-induced + 250mg/kg of *Jatropha tanjorensis* extract for 28 days

Group 13: DOX-induced + 250mg/kg of *Jatropha tanjorensis* extract for 42 days

Group 14: DOX-induced + 500mg/kg of *Jatropha tanjorensis* extract for 14 days

Group 15: DOX-induced + 500mg/kg of *Jatropha tanjorensis* extract for 28 days

Group 16: DOX-induced + 500mg/kg of *Jatropha tanjorensis* extract for 42 days

Methods

At the end of 14, 28 and 42 days of oral treatment with the *Jatropha tanjorensis* extract, the rats were humanely sacrificed through cervical dislocation, blood samples were collected for biochemical investigation and hearts collected, homogenized and the supernatant was collected for biochemical assay. Some other heart tissues were fixed in 10% formalin for histopathological studies.

Determination of Cardiac Function Markers

The plasma troponin T and I, Interleukin-6 (IL-6) were determined using ELISA kit as described by Aarden *et al* (1987) and Sabaheta *et al* (2007). C-reactive protein (CRP) was determined using Latex turbidimetric photometric method as reported by Tietz (1999).

Determination of Activities of Cardiac Enzymes of Heart Homogenate

Creatine kinase and lactate dehydrogenase activities were determined using the method described by Marvin and Charles (1959). The activities of ALT, AST and ALP were determined using Randox Kits according to the method of Reitman and Frankel (1957).

Determination of Plasma markers of Liver Function

The estimation of total protein concentration and albumin concentration as well as activities of ALT, ALP and AST were determined using Randox Kits according to the method of Reitman and Frankel (1957). Total bilirubin was determined by colorimetric method as described by Jendrassik and Grof (1938).

Determination of Plasma Lipid Profile

The photometric method described by Freidman *et al* (2003) was used to determine Total-CHOL, LDL, HDL and VLDL. The triglyceride concentration was assayed according to the method reported by Peter and Kwiterovich (2004).

Oxidative Stress Marker Identification

Catalase activity was determined using the method described by Beers and Sizer (1952). The activity of superoxide dismutase was measured using the method previously described by Maier *et al* (2019). The method used by Rotruck *et al.*, (1973) to determine glutathione peroxidase activity was used. The malondialdehyde concentration was determined using a modified Gutteridge and Wilkins method

(1982). Sedlak and Lindsay's method (1968) was used to determine the reduced glutathione concentration.

Histopathological Analysis

The hearts from the rats were collected after sacrifice and subjected to histological investigation. The procedure was according to the method previously described by Asiwe *et al* (2022).

Statistical Analysis

Results were analyzed and presented as mean \pm standard error of mean (M \pm SEM) using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 18.0. Descriptive statistics was done by one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and multiple comparisons were done using Turkey Post Hoc at (P \leq 0.05) confidence interval.

3. Results

Phytochemical Screening

Table 1 shows the concentration of the phytochemicals present in the diethylether extract of the plant sample. The flavonoid content was 9.78 ± 0.1 mg/100g, Saponin was 12.80 ± 2.4 mg/100g, alkaloid – 1.1 ± 0.1 mg/100g, anthraquinone was 1.2 ± 0.1 mg/100g and steroid was 0.46 ± 0.12 mg/100g.

Effect of Diethylether Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* on Cardiac Function Markers

In the present study, the groups treated with the plant extract at 167 mg/kg, 250 mg/kg and 500 mg/kg showed a significant (p \leq 0.05) decrease in CTnT, CTnI, IL-6 and CRP when compared with the negative control groups. The group administered 250mg/kg of the extract for 28 days shows non-significant (p \leq 0.05) difference when compared with the group treated with 2mg/kg carvedilol (positive control) (Table 2).

Effect of Diethylether Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* on Cardiac Enzymes

It was observed that induction with 20mg/kg b.wt of doxorubicin in the negative control groups showed a significant increase (p \leq 0.05) in CK (285.20 ± 2.03 , 254.40 ± 5.03 , 237.60 ± 0.75 U/L), ALT (35.60 ± 0.75 , 27.80 ± 0.37 , 24.20 ± 0.20 IU/L), ALP (316.60 ± 2.91 , 228.80 ± 2.03 , 195.40 ± 3.04 U/L), AST (35.20 ± 0.92 , 27.40 ± 0.68 , 24.00 ± 0.55 IU/L), and LDH (551.00 ± 0.55 , 551.20 ± 2.24 , 540.40 ± 0.24 U/L), for 14, 28 and 42 days respectively when compared to the normal control. Groups treated with 167mg/kg, 250mg/kg and 500mg/kg of the extract showed a significant decrease (p \leq 0.05) in the activities of CK, ALT, ALP, AST and LDH when compared to the negative control (Table 3).

Effect of Diethylether Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* on Plasma Markers of Liver Function

The result shows significant (p \leq 0.05) decrease in total protein (56.60 ± 0.24 , 46.20 ± 0.37 , 47.40 ± 0.40 g/L), albumin (21.60 ± 0.24 , 18.60 ± 0.24 , 16.60 ± 0.24 mmol/L),

and an increase in TBIL (18.24 ± 0.04 , 19.86 ± 0.19 , $16.34 \pm 0.23\mu\text{mol/L}$), ALT (33.20 ± 0.37 , 26.40 ± 0.98 , $31.60 \pm 0.24\text{IU/L}$), ALP (168.20 ± 0.37 , 197.20 ± 0.49 , $194.20 \pm 4.20 \text{ U/L}$), AST (32.60 ± 2.44 , 45.00 ± 0.84 , $46.60 \pm 0.24 \text{ IU/L}$) in the negative control respectively for 14, 28 and 42 days when compared to the normal control. Treatment with the plant extract at 167mg/kg, 250mg/kg and 500mg/kg b.wt for 14, 28 and 42 days significantly increased ($p \leq 0.05$) the levels of total protein and albumin and lowered the levels of TBIL, ALT, ALP and AST (Table 4)

Effect of Diethylether Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* on Plasma Lipid Profile

The result (Table 5) shows a significant increase in Total – CHOL (8.58 ± 0.05 , 8.50 ± 0.05 , $9.04 \pm 0.02\text{mmol/L}$), LDL-CHOL (1.58 ± 0.01 , 1.63 ± 0.04 , $1.74 \pm 0.06\text{mmol/L}$), VLDL-CHOL (1.59 ± 0.00 , 1.85 ± 0.01 , $1.82 \pm 0.01\text{mmol/L}$) and TG (3.62 ± 0.01 , 3.71 ± 0.06 , $3.55 \pm 0.02\text{mmol/L}$), and a decrease in HDL-CHOL (0.59 ± 0.04 , 0.52 ± 0.19 , $0.50 \pm 0.03\text{mmol/L}$) when compared to the normal control. Treatment with the plant extract at 167mg/kg, 250mg/kg and 500mg/kg b.wt for 14, 28 and 42 days significantly decreased ($p \leq 0.05$) the levels of total- CHOL, LDL-CHOL, VLDL-CHOL and TG while elevating the level of HDL-CHOL.

Effect of Diethylether Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* on Oxidative Stress Markers

The result (Table 6) shows significantly elevated ($p \leq 0.05$) level of MDA (41.90 ± 0.66 , 40.94 ± 0.19 , $44.60 \pm 0.85\text{nmol}$) in the negative control relative to the normal control. There was a significant decrease in GSH level and GPx, CAT, SOD activities for the negative control when compared to the normal control. Treatment with *Jatropha tanjorensis* extract at 167mg/kg, 250mg/kg and 500mg/kg b.wt significantly decreased MDA level and increased levels of GSH, GPx, CAT and SOD. At 500mg/kg b.wt MDA level significantly decreased to 13.03 ± 0.74 , 12.89 ± 0.06 and $12.65 \pm 0.41\text{nmol/L}$ for 14, 28 and 42days when compared to 41.90 ± 0.66 , 40.94 ± 0.19 , $44.60 \pm 0.85\text{nmol/L}$ for 14, 28 and 42 days respectively for the negative control.

Histopathological Findings

The photomicrograph of the normal control (plate 1) shows normal histology with cardiac myofibrils (MF), blood vessels (BV) and central nuclei (Nu). Plate 2 shows the photomicrograph of heart tissue of negative control with distorted heart architecture, the cardiac myofibrils are fibrotic showing disintegration of myocytes. Plate 3 shows the positive control with normal cardiac tissue and homogenous fiber diameter. Plate 4-6 shows the photomicrographs for groups treated with 167 mg/kg of the extract for 14, 28 and 42 days. It shows mild distortion with devitalized tissues (DT). Plate 7-9 shows the photomicrographs for groups treated with 250mg/kg of the extract; it reveals normal myocytes and regeneration of cardiac myofibrils (MF). Plate 10-12 shows the photomicrographs for groups treated with 500mg/kg of the extract for 14, 28 and 42 days. It shows normal myocytes and nuclei comparable to those of normal control (plate 1)

Table 1. Qualitative Phytochemical Composition of Leaves of *Jatropha tanjorensis*

Phytochemical	Concentration (mg/100 g)
Alkaloid	1.1 ± 0.1
Anthraquinone	1.2 ± 0.1
Flavonoid	9.78 ± 0.1
Saponin	12.80 ± 2.4
Steroid	0.46 ± 0.12
Tannin	5.7 ± 0.4
Terpenoid	6.7 ± 1.6
Total	37.74 ± 4.82

Values are reported as mean ± standard error of mean (M±SEM)

Table 2. Effect of Diethylether Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf on Plasma Cardiac Function Markers

Treatment	CTn-T (ng/L)	CTn-I (ng/L)	IL-6 (pg/L)	CRP (mg/dl)
Normal control	32.72±0.76 ^a	54.72±2.41 ^a	98.76±0.63 ^a	0.16±0.01 ^a
Neg. Control 14 days	75.80±0.58 ^{a,b}	83.60±0.24 ^{a,b}	190.60±0.60 ^{a,b}	2.13±0.02 ^{a,b}
Neg. Control 28 days	69.80±0.37 ^{a,c}	72.80±1.83 ^{a,c}	169.60±0.19 ^{a,c}	2.05±0.02 ^{a,c}
Neg. Control 42 days	67.80±0.58 ^{a,d}	61.20±2.89 ^{a,d}	169.60±0.60 ^{a,d}	2.09±0.00 ^{a,d}
Pos. Control 14 days	45.76±0.58 ^e	54.80±1.62 ^e	87.80±0.37 ^e	0.07±0.00 ^e
Pos. Control 28 days	35.10±0.35 ^f	49.40±1.43 ^f	96.20±0.37 ^g	0.07±0.00 ^f
Pos. Control 42 days	28.88±0.34 ^g	50.20±0.86 ^g	90.60±0.68 ^f	0.16±0.01 ^g
167 mg/kg 14 days	50.56±0.17 ^{b,e}	52.80±0.37 ^b	87.80±0.37 ^b	0.12±0.00 ^{b,e}
167 mg/kg 28 days	51.36±0.24 ^c	50.22±0.98 ^c	85.64±0.32 ^{c,g}	0.13±0.01 ^{c,f}
167 mg/kg 42 days	49.00±0.17 ^{d,g}	49.62±0.34 ^d	83.18±1.30 ^{d,f}	0.11±0.00 ^g
250 mg/kg 14 days	48.26±0.54 ^{b,e}	47.80±0.41 ^{b,e}	79.12±1.40 ^{b,e}	0.09±0.00 ^b
250 mg/kg 28 days	42.32±0.81 ^{c,f}	49.30±0.37 ^c	75.58±0.25 ^{c,g}	0.09±0.00 ^c
250 mg/kg 42 days	38.60±0.66 ^{d,g}	47.80±0.41 ^d	73.60±0.51 ^{d,f}	0.09±0.00 ^g
500 mg/kg 14 days	37.42±0.91 ^{b,e}	34.26±0.10 ^{b,e}	71.60±0.51 ^{b,e}	0.09±0.02 ^b
500 mg/kg 28 days	26.90±0.83 ^{c,f}	29.16±1.00 ^{c,f}	72.20±0.37 ^{c,g}	0.11±0.00 ^{c,f}
500 mg/kg 42 days	19.90±0.98 ^{d,g}	26.04±0.39 ^{d,g}	71.80±0.37 ^{d,f}	0.06±0.00 ^{d,g}

Values are reported as mean ± standard error of mean (M±SEM) (n =5). Values with similar superscript letters indicate significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) down the column while those without or different superscripts show non-significant differences ($p \geq 0.05$) down the column when compared with the untreated, extract, and reference drug groups.

Table 3. Effect of Diethylether Extract of *Jatrophanjorensis* Cardiac Enzyme Activities

Treatment	CK (U/L)	ALT(IU/L)	ALP(U/L)	AST(IU/L)	LDH(U/L)
Normal control	112.80±6.97 ^a	14.00±0.00 ^a	117.00±0.45 ^a	15.00±0.55 ^a	141.60±2.32 ^a
Neg. Control 14 days	285.20±2.03 ^{a,b}	35.60±0.75 ^{a,b}	316.60±2.91 ^{a,b}	35.20±0.92 ^{a,b}	551.00±0.55 ^{a,b}
Neg. Control 28 days	254.40±5.03 ^{a,c}	27.80±0.37 ^{a,c}	228.80±2.03 ^{a,c}	27.40±0.68 ^{a,c}	551.20±2.24 ^{a,c}
Neg. Control 42 days	237.60±0.75 ^{a,d}	24.20±0.20 ^{a,d}	195.40±3.04 ^{a,d}	24.00±0.55 ^{a,d}	540.40±0.24 ^{a,d}
Pos. Control 14 days	140.80±2.92 ^e	16.60±1.08 ^e	179.40±0.75 ^e	17.60±0.24 ^e	216.00±4.04 ^e
Pos. Control 28 days	151.60±2.27 ^f	13.60±0.24 ^f	119.40±0.68 ^f	14.80±0.37 ^f	160.40±1.47 ^f
Pos. Control 42 days	116.20±3.14 ^g	11.60±0.24 ^g	99.40±2.44 ^g	12.20±0.37 ^g	137.80±1.28 ^g
167 mg/kg 14 days	243.80±2.01 ^b	13.60±0.24 ^{b,e}	162.00±1.34 ^{b,e}	21.60±0.60 ^b	247.40±1.57 ^{b,e}
167 mg/kg 28 days	192.60±2.75 ^{c,f}	13.60±0.24 ^c	128.60±1.12 ^c	18.20±0.49 ^{c,f}	209.20±4.03 ^{c,f}
167 mg/kg 42 days	157.20±1.36 ^{d,g}	13.20±0.49 ^{d,g}	110.60±1.12 ^{d,g}	15.20±0.49 ^{d,g}	160.60±0.24 ^{d,g}
250 mg/kg 14 days	113.60±1.12 ^{b,e}	12.00±0.55 ^{b,e}	127.60±1.40 ^{b,e}	15.60±0.40 ^{b,e}	209.00±5.39 ^{b,e}
250 mg/kg 28 days	101.80±1.80 ^c	12.40±0.60 ^c	93.20±1.15 ^{c,f}	11.80±0.73 ^{c,f}	162.80±1.20 ^{c,f}
250 mg/kg 42 days	127.60±1.22 ^{d,g}	12.80±0.37 ^d	116.80±1.71 ^{d,g}	11.20±0.37 ^{d,g}	107.00±1.34 ^{d,g}
500 mg/kg 14 days	103.60±1.44 ^{b,e}	11.20±0.37 ^{b,e}	109.60±1.22 ^{b,e}	15.80±0.37 ^{b,e}	189.20±2.24 ^{b,e}
500 mg/kg 28 days	96.20±1.32 ^{c,f}	11.40±0.24 ^{c,f}	87.40±1.29 ^{c,f}	9.60±1.08 ^{c,f}	103.40±2.01 ^{c,f}
500 mg/kg 42 days	83.00±1.64 ^{d,g}	10.40±0.40 ^d	82.00±0.55 ^{d,g}	7.80±0.49 ^{d,g}	94.80±1.32 ^{d,g}

Values are reported as mean ± standard error of mean (M±SEM) (n =5). Values with similar superscript letters indicate significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) down the column while those without or different superscripts show non-significant differences ($p \geq 0.05$) down the column when compared with the untreated, extract, and reference drug groups.

Table 4. Effect of Diethylether Extract of *Jatrophanjorensis* on Liver Function Markers

Treatment	TP (g/L)	ALB (mmol/L)	TBIL (μ mol/L)	ALT (IU/L)	ALP(U/L)	AST(IU/L)
Normal control	65.60 \pm 0.24 ^a	39.60 \pm 0.40 ^a	13.34 \pm 0.60 ^a	13.20 \pm 0.49 ^a	128.20 \pm 3.83 ^a	17.00 \pm 0.00 ^a
Neg. Control 14 days	56.60 \pm 0.24 ^{a,b}	21.60 \pm 0.24 ^{a,b}	18.24 \pm 0.04 ^{a,b}	33.20 \pm 0.37 ^{a,b}	168.20 \pm 0.37 ^{a,b}	32.60 \pm 2.44 ^{a,b}
Neg. Control 28 days	46.20 \pm 0.37 ^{a,c}	18.60 \pm 0.24 ^{a,c}	19.86 \pm 0.19 ^{a,c}	26.40 \pm 0.98 ^{a,c}	197.20 \pm 0.49 ^{a,c}	45.00 \pm 0.84 ^{a,c}
Neg. Control 42 days	47.40 \pm 0.40 ^{a,d}	16.60 \pm 0.24 ^{a,d}	19.34 \pm 0.23 ^{a,d}	31.60 \pm 0.24 ^{a,d}	194.20 \pm 4.20 ^{a,d}	46.60 \pm 0.24 ^{a,d}
Pos. Control 14 days	61.20 \pm 0.37 ^e	38.60 \pm 0.24 ^e	12.62 \pm 0.09 ^e	17.96 \pm 0.02 ^e	134.20 \pm 0.37 ^e	16.80 \pm 0.20 ^e
Pos. Control 28 days	65.00 \pm 0.55 ^f	38.60 \pm 0.24 ^f	13.08 \pm 0.07 ^f	11.92 \pm 0.05 ^f	134.40 \pm 0.24 ^f	15.60 \pm 0.24 ^f
Pos. Control 42 days	61.20 \pm 0.49 ^g	41.20 \pm 0.37 ^g	13.00 \pm 0.05 ^g	11.96 \pm 0.02 ^g	113.80 \pm 1.16 ^g	16.40 \pm 0.24 ^g
167 mg/kg 14 days	59.80 \pm 0.20 ^{b,e}	40.00 \pm 0.00 ^b	13.10 \pm 0.25 ^b	14.00 \pm 0.00 ^{b,e}	191.40 \pm 1.91 ^{b,e}	17.60 \pm 0.60 ^b
167 mg/kg 28 days	60.20 \pm 0.37 ^{c,f}	38.00 \pm 0.55 ^c	13.80 \pm 0.05 ^{c,f}	15.60 \pm 1.47 ^{c,f}	122.00 \pm 4.09 ^{c,f}	16.40 \pm 0.24 ^c
167 mg/kg 42 days	61.40 \pm 0.24 ^d	37.20 \pm 0.49 ^{d,g}	13.04 \pm 0.17 ^d	16.40 \pm 0.98 ^{d,g}	118.00 \pm 4.00 ^d	13.80 \pm 0.80 ^d
250 mg/kg 14 days	66.20 \pm 0.37 ^{b,e}	39.20 \pm 0.37 ^b	12.98 \pm 0.28 ^b	8.00 \pm 0.00 ^{b,e}	117.60 \pm 1.83 ^{b,e}	12.60 \pm 1.29 ^{b,e}
250 mg/kg 28 days	69.20 \pm 0.37 ^{c,f}	39.80 \pm 0.20 ^{c,f}	12.10 \pm 0.36 ^{c,f}	7.80 \pm 0.12 ^{c,f}	106.40 \pm 0.93 ^{c,f}	16.60 \pm 1.12 ^c
250 mg/kg 42 days	71.00 \pm 0.00 ^{d,g}	40.00 \pm 0.00 ^d	11.18 \pm 0.44 ^{d,g}	7.60 \pm 0.10 ^{d,g}	113.20 \pm 1.56 ^d	13.80 \pm 1.36 ^{d,g}
500 mg/kg 14 days	71.60 \pm 0.93 ^{b,e}	43.20 \pm 1.32 ^b	11.66 \pm 0.11 ^{b,e}	5.60 \pm 0.98 ^{b,e}	94.60 \pm 5.47 ^{b,e}	15.20 \pm 0.92 ^b
500 mg/kg 28 days	70.40 \pm 0.24 ^{c,f}	45.40 \pm 1.08 ^{c,e}	10.78 \pm 0.07 ^{c,f}	6.80 \pm 0.73 ^{c,f}	99.40 \pm 5.62 ^{c,f}	14.20 \pm 0.73 ^c
500 mg/kg 42 days	71.60 \pm 0.24 ^{d,g}	46.00 \pm 0.84 ^{d,g}	10.50 \pm 0.17 ^{d,g}	6.40 \pm 0.98 ^{d,g}	77.00 \pm 0.45 ^{d,g}	12.80 \pm 0.92 ^{d,g}

Values are reported as mean \pm standard error of mean (M \pm SEM) (n =5). Values with similar superscript letters indicate significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) down the column while those without or different superscripts show non-significant differences ($p \geq 0.05$) down the column when compared with the untreated, extract, and reference drug groups.

Table 5. Effect of Diethylether Extract of *Jatrophanjorensis* on Plasma Lipid Profile

Treatment	Total-CHOL (mmol/L)	HDL-CHOL (mmol/L)	LDL-CHOL (mmol/L)	VLDL-CHOL (mmol/L)	TG (mmol/L)
Normal control	5.66±0.02 ^a	0.97±0.07 ^a	0.19±0.04 ^a	1.21±0.08 ^a	2.51±0.17 ^a
Neg. Control 14 days	8.58±0.05 ^{a,b}	0.59±0.04 ^{a,b}	1.58±0.01 ^{a,b}	1.59±0.00 ^{a,b}	3.62±0.01 ^{a,b}
Neg. Control 28 days	8.50±0.05 ^{a,c}	0.52±0.19 ^{a,c}	1.63±0.04 ^{a,c}	1.85±0.01 ^{a,c}	3.71±0.06 ^{a,c}
Neg. Control 42 days	9.04±0.02 ^{a,d}	0.50±0.03 ^{a,d}	1.74±0.06 ^{a,d}	1.82±0.01 ^{a,d}	3.55±0.02 ^{a,d}
Pos. Control 14 days	5.64±0.07 ^e	1.00±0.02 ^e	0.15±0.02 ^e	0.87±0.03 ^e	2.11±0.01 ^e
Pos. Control 28 days	6.00±0.05 ^f	1.05±0.02 ^f	0.06±0.00	0.65±0.02 ^f	1.41±0.01 ^f
Pos. Control 42 days	6.26±0.02 ^g	1.03±0.12 ^g	0.10±0.02 ^f	1.24±0.05 ^g	1.77±0.01 ^g
167 mg/kg 14 days	5.90±0.12 ^b	1.02±0.35 ^b	0.41±0.02 ^{b,e}	0.89±0.11 ^b	1.61±0.15 ^{b,e}
167 mg/kg 28 days	6.20±0.17 ^c	1.04±0.13 ^c	0.14±0.06 ^c	0.85±0.04 ^c	1.75±0.12 ^{c,f}
167 mg/kg 42 days	6.20±0.15 ^d	0.97±0.08 ^d	0.50±0.04 ^{d,f}	1.11±0.06 ^d	1.67±0.19 ^d
250 mg/kg 14 days	5.88±0.14 ^b	1.03±0.12 ^b	0.14±0.04 ^b	0.91±0.01 ^b	1.45±0.13 ^{b,e}
250 mg/kg 28 days	6.44±0.07 ^{c,f}	1.12±0.09 ^{c,f}	0.42±0.03 ^c	1.14±0.01 ^{c,f}	1.26±0.10 ^c
250 mg/kg 42 days	4.98±0.32 ^{d,g}	1.14±0.03 ^{d,g}	0.21±0.06 ^{d,f}	1.12±0.03 ^d	1.73±0.08 ^d
500 mg/kg 14 days	3.76±0.26 ^{b,e}	1.07±0.03 ^{b,e}	0.18±0.02 ^b	0.80±0.09 ^{b,e}	1.32±0.09 ^{b,e}
500 mg/kg 28 days	3.48±0.05 ^{c,f}	1.30±0.04 ^{c,f}	0.12±0.02 ^c	0.69±0.10 ^c	1.26±0.08 ^c
500 mg/kg 42 days	3.76±0.27 ^{d,g}	1.42±0.05 ^{d,g}	0.10±0.03 ^d	0.39±0.02 ^{d,g}	1.43±0.13 ^{d,g}

Values are reported as mean ± standard error of mean (M±SEM) (n =5). Values with similar superscript letters indicate significant differences (p≤ 0.05) down the column while those without or different superscripts show non-significant differences (p≥ 0.05) down the column when compared with the untreated, extract, and reference drug groups.

Table 6. Effect of Diethylether Extract of *Jatrophanjorensis* on Oxidative Stress Markers

Treatment	MDA (nmol/L)	GSH (mmol/gHb)	GPx (ng/ml)	CAT (mU/L)	SOD (u/ml)
Normal control	25.37±0.79 ^a	75.28±0.65 ^a	4.22±0.04 ^a	115.70±0.11 ^a	35.27±0.72 ^a
Neg. Control 14 days	41.90±0.66 ^{a,b}	31.24±0.51 ^{a,b}	1.91±0.76 ^{a,b}	52.96±0.86 ^{a,b}	10.52±1.36 ^{a,b}
Neg. Control 28 days	40.94±0.19 ^{a,c}	24.56±1.66 ^{a,c}	1.70±1.35 ^{a,c}	52.91±0.24 ^{a,c}	12.05±0.02 ^{a,c}
Neg. Control 42 days	44.60±0.85 ^{a,d}	35.02±0.28 ^{a,d}	1.50±0.58 ^{a,d}	50.48±0.56 ^{a,d}	11.78±0.32 ^{a,d}
Pos. Control 14 days	33.26±0.89 ^e	79.04±1.75 ^e	4.54±0.14 ^e	118.95±0.25 ^e	29.84±2.82 ^e
Pos. Control 28 days	27.60±0.24 ^f	77.92±0.20 ^f	3.70±0.16	119.48±0.24 ^f	30.36±0.46 ^f
Pos. Control 42 days	19.90±0.10 ^g	83.24±2.80 ^g	3.36±0.17	115.60±0.04 ^g	33.16±0.68 ^g
167 mg/kg 14 days	28.51±0.23 ^{b,e}	72.02±0.28 ^{b,e}	4.90±0.05 ^{b,e}	112.83±0.57 ^{b,e}	31.36±1.90 ^b
167 mg/kg 28 days	23.17±0.45 ^{c,f}	76.74±0.95 ^c	3.56±0.14 ^c	111.11±0.77 ^{c,f}	26.57±0.52 ^c
167 mg/kg 42 days	19.56±0.54 ^d	74.40±0.47 ^{d,g}	4.42±0.15 ^d	118.50±0.13 ^{d,g}	26.92±1.06 ^d
250 mg/kg 14 days	18.05±0.68 ^{b,e}	82.08±0.79 ^{b,e}	3.98±0.17 ^b	112.62±0.14 ^{b,e}	21.50±0.53 ^{b,e}
250 mg/kg 28 days	17.47±0.93 ^{c,f}	82.84±1.70 ^{c,f}	3.62±0.23 ^c	113.84±0.27 ^{c,f}	22.99±0.88 ^{c,f}
250 mg/kg 42 days	17.24±0.51 ^{d,g}	83.14±1.54 ^d	4.04±0.12 ^d	119.84±0.30 ^{d,g}	24.64±1.04 ^{d,g}
500 mg/kg 14 days	13.03±0.74 ^{b,e}	88.22±0.61 ^{b,e}	5.22±0.18 ^b	119.99±0.51 ^b	23.88±0.77 ^{b,e}
500 mg/kg 28 days	12.89±0.06 ^{c,f}	87.94±1.61 ^{c,f}	5.46±0.07 ^c	118.05±0.01 ^{c,f}	23.71±0.75 ^{d,f}
500 mg/kg 42 days	12.65±0.41 ^{d,g}	87.14±0.72 ^{d,g}	4.76±0.15 ^d	118.91±0.09 ^{d,g}	20.81±0.46 ^g

Values are reported as mean ± standard error of mean (M±SEM) (n =5). Values with similar superscript letters indicate significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) down the column while those without or different superscripts show non-significant differences ($p \geq 0.05$) down the column when compared with the untreated, extract, and reference drug groups.

Figure 1: Plate 1-photomicrograph of normal control, plate 2-photomicrograph of negative control; plate 3-photomicrograph of positive control. Plates 4-6: photomicrographs of groups treated with 167/mg/kg of the plant extract for 14, 28 and 42 days. Plates 7-9: photomicrographs of groups treated with 250mg/kg of the plant extract for 14, 28 and 42 days. Plates 10-12: photomicrographs of groups treated with 500mg/kg of the plant extract for 14, 28 and 42 days. Magnification X400, H & E. MF (myofibrils); FB (fibrocyte), NU (Nuclei). DT (Devalitized tissue), KL (Karyolysis), BV (Blood vessel), VAC (vacuolation).

4. Discussion

The effect of *Jatropha tanjorensis* diethylether extract on cardiac function markers, liver functions, lipid profile, antioxidant activity as well as heart histology in doxorubicin-induced cardiotoxicity in rats was investigated in this study. Because of the abundance of phytochemical constituents, *Jatropha tanjorensis* reduced doxorubicin-induced cardiac toxicity. Our research found the presence of important bioactive compounds like alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, steroids, tannins, and terpenoids. The findings of this study were consistent with previous reports of Usin and colleagues, (2022). Notably, flavonoids are water-soluble polyphenolic molecules with antioxidant activity that have numerous beneficial effects on the cardiovascular system (Jucá *et al.*, 2020). They also prevent the oxidation of low-density lipoprotein and lower cholesterol and triglyceride levels in the blood (Gulcin *et al.*, 2020). Saponins have also been shown to lower blood cholesterol levels (Kareem *et al.*, 2022), while tannins have been shown to prevent a variety of illnesses, including heart disease (Singh and Kumar 2020). The presence of these active constituents could have contributed to the cardioprotective properties of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaves.

Cardiac function biomarkers are proteins/enzymes that are used as primary and secondary prevention, diagnosis and management tools in cardiology for myocardial infarction and other heart-related problems (Mukherjee and Mukherjee, 2021). Troponins are regulatory proteins that are found in both skeletal and cardiac muscle

and are essential for muscle contraction. The calcium-mediated interaction between actin and myosin is regulated by cardiac troponin 1 (Sharma *et al.*, 2022). The higher levels of CTn-T and CTn-I in the DOX-exposed animals imply that doxorubicin caused cardiac damage. However, the levels of CTn-T and CTn-I were reduced after administration of the plant extract at doses of 167mg/kg, 250mg/kg, and 500mg/kg, implying that the plant extract alleviated the doxorubicin-induced cardiac damage which was consistent with the findings of Zhang et al (2022). Inflammation has been linked to an increased risk of major adverse cardiovascular events and death (Jaiswal and Libby 2020). The significant increase in plasma CRP and IL-6 levels in the DOX-exposed animals suggest cardiac inflammatory reactions which precede damage. However, the decrease observed after 14, 28, and 42 days of treatment with the diethylether extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* demonstrates the plant's ability to mitigate inflammatory reactions. The presence of elevated AST and LDH levels in DOX-exposed animals supports previous findings and reports that doxorubicin caused cardiac damage (Sheibani *et al.*, 2022). According to Ramani Sattiraju et al. (2020), increased enzyme activity may indicate a loss of myocyte membrane integrity. Meanwhile, Doxorubicin may have promoted myocyte membrane degeneration through free radical production, resulting in enzyme leakage. The *Jatropha tanjorensis* significantly reduced elevated AST and LDH levels which further demonstrates its rich phytochemical constituents responsible for abating free radical production. Creatine Kinase (CK) is a reversible enzyme that catalyzes the conversion of creatine and ATP to creatine phosphate and ADP. In this study, *Jatropha tanjorensis* extracts significantly reduced the CK level particularly at 500mg/kg for 42 days, against the increase caused by doxorubicin on the cardiac tissues. Induction of oxidative stress is one of the pathological mechanisms of Doxorubicin toxicity. However, GSH, GPx, GR, SOD, and catalase are antioxidant defense system that protects the body from oxidative stress-induced tissue damage (Sheibani *et al.*, 2022). GSH is widely regarded as the most important intracellular hydrophilic antioxidant, protecting cells from free radical damage (Michalak, 2022). Doxorubicin has been shown to cause an excess of hydrogen peroxide and superoxide radical formation (Li *et al.*, 2021). This could explain the significantly lowered levels of GSH, GPx, CAT, and SOD in DOX-exposed animals. Lipid peroxidation is one of the effects of free radical generation. The reactive form of ROS, the hydroxyl radical (OH⁻), can initiate lipid peroxidation by attacking polyunsaturated fatty acids (Michalak, 2022). Malondialdehyde, a lipid peroxidation by-product was observed to be considerably high in DOX-exposed animals particularly for the 42-day period. Treatment with *Jatropha tanjorensis* reduced MDA while increasing GSH, GPx, catalase, and SOD levels. This can be attributed to the abundant flavonoids and polyphenolic compounds present in the plant; this observation is consistent with the findings of Afsar et al. (2021), who reported the free radical scavenging potentials of *Acacia hydaspica* extract. The lipid profile indices are useful for monitoring the cardiovascular system's health. According to Imaizumi *et al.*, (2022), high levels of TG and LDL-C may predispose to cardiovascular disease whereas a higher level of HDL-C, on the other hand, is associated with a lower risk of cardiovascular disease. Doxorubicin showed a significant increase in total-CHOL, LDL-CHOL, VLDL, and TG levels but a decrease in HDL-C levels in this study. Treatment with *Jatropha tanjorensis* diethylether

extract at 167, 250, and 500mg/kg for 14, 28, and 42 days caused a significant increase in HDL while decreasing Total-CHOL, LDL-C, and TG, indicating the extract's ability to improve total cholesterol, HDL, LDL-C, VLDL-C, and triglyceride metabolism in rats which is consistent with previous findings of Imaizumi *et al.*, (2022). Total protein, albumin, and total bilirubin are biomarkers that can be used to predict the health of the liver. Significant decreases in serum or plasma total protein and albumin concentrations, accompanied by increase in bilirubin levels and AST, ALP, GGT, and ALT activities, are indicators of liver compromise and hepatotoxicity (Eruotor *et al.*, 2022). Reactive oxygen species produced by chemical agents damage the membranes of hepatic tissues, resulting in protein and enzyme leakage into the blood. Doxorubicin administration increased ALP, ALT, and AST levels while decreasing total protein and albumin levels. This implies that it interferes with the machinery involved in protein synthesis in the liver. However, consistent with previous studies of Eruotor *et al.* (2022), the plant extract significantly reduced the levels of AST, ALT, ALP, and TBIL while increasing total protein and albumin concentrations. This suggests that the extract ameliorated doxorubicin-induced hepatotoxicity.

The gold standard for detecting acute doxorubicin-induced cardiotoxicity is the examination of histological changes in myocardial tissue (Al-Kuraishy *et al.*, 2022). Doxorubicin causes a considerable degree of heart architecture distortion, myocardial fiber disorganization, myofibrillar loss, and heavy inflammation which was consistent with the findings of Ebrahim *et al.* (2022). The plant extract, especially at 500mg/kg, reversed the histological changes and stimulated myocyte regeneration. These reversible changes in myocardial tissues point to the leaf extract's cardioprotective properties.

5. Conclusion

The study suggests that *Jatropha tanjorensis* offered cardioprotection as assessed through biochemical markers and histological examination in doxorubicin-induced cardiac damage the leaf extract may have acted as a cardioprotectant by replenishing cardiomyocytes with antioxidants that protected against doxorubicin-induced oxidative stress. The extract's cardioprotective effect may be attributed to suppression of oxidative stress and inflammatory reactions in the heart which leads to positive cardiac remodeling. If the plant's protective function is confirmed in cancer patients, it may be used as adjuvant therapy.

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Authors' Contributions

CCM and CJJ designed the study, OEE carried out the experimental protocol including photochemistry and animal handling. OEE carried out the statistical analysis of data and the interpretation of data as well as manuscript writing.

Data availability statement

The entire data for the study has been included in this manuscript

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Ethical consideration

The study was approved by the ethical committee of the University of Port-Harcourt (UPH-REC/2021/028) which followed strictly with National guidelines for animal care and use of animals as well as the Organization of Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD)

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